

Pharmacists Awareness of Covid-19 and Its Symptoms in King Hussein Hospital at RMS, Jordan

Nada Al Azab*, Mai Falahat, Esraa Alawneh, Raya Adaileh, Farah Adaileh
Pharmacy Department, RMS, Jordan

Abstract— Objectives: Corona virus (COVID-19) first detected in China at the end of 2019 and many cases of deaths related to the virus have been described worldwide. Pharmacists show an important role in assigning precise information about the virus to the community. The aim of this study is to evaluate the Awareness and knowledge among Pharmacists and co pharmacists working at (KMH) about COVID-19 and symptoms associated with the infection. **Methods:** A questionnaire will be distributed to pharmacists and pharmacist assistants working in the hospital. The questionnaire is divided into two parts, the first part is concerned with the topographic information of the participants, while the second part consists of a set of questions concerned with the knowledge and experience of the participants and their information about the nature of the disease and the virus and its symptoms. The results will be analyzed using SSPS software version 21. **Results:** A total of 100 pharmacists and pharmacist assistants participated in the questionnaire, the majority of whom were female (n = 66), (62%) of the participants were between the ages of 30-39, (79%) were married, the majority hold a bachelor's degree by (69%). There is a commitment of wearing mask, with a significant difference (24.82% and 48.18% p=.0001). Most of the participants have a good and updated data about corona virus and how the virus transmitted (89%). **Conclusion:** From this study, we conclude that pharmacists and pharmacist assistants at King Hussein Hospital have sufficient awareness of this global epidemic and its accompanying symptoms. This positive and high level of knowledge affects the rest of the people working and not working in this health sector in a positive way.

Keywords— Awareness, pharmacist, Covid-19.

I. INTRODUCTION

Corona virus (COVID-19) first detected in China at the end of 2019 and many cases of deaths related to the virus have been described worldwide [1]

In almost every country in the world some positive cases of COVID-19 and several deaths have been reported due to the outbreak of this virus.[2] Corona viruses are from the old family of viruses that can cause mild illnesses, such as the common cold, and some more serious diseases, such as Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS)-COV or SARS-COV. SARS-COV-2, which is currently the cause of the global pandemic and was the subject of this survey, is a virus of this family. Multiple corona viruses are primarily of animal origin and can cause disease in humans as a result of transmission from animals. The most common symptoms of infection with the disease are coughing, fever and shortness of breath. In some cases, pneumonia, severe acute respiratory syndrome, kidney failure, and death may occur [3]. It was noted that some people with comorbidities (such as heart disease and diabetes) may be more susceptible to infection and the death rate may be high in this population group.[4]

Until now, there is no precise, effective, confirmed, pharmacological treatment or prophylaxis. Even though no drug has been settled for this infection, it has been proposed that some present drugs can be used for treatment. [6]

As healthcare professionals, pharmacists show an important role in handover accurate information about COVID-19 to the public. The aim of the current study was to assess the awareness of pharmacists' about COVID-19 and its symptoms

II. METHODS

A questionnaire distributed to pharmacists and pharmacist assistants working in the hospital. The questionnaire is divided

into two parts, the first part is concerned with the topographic information of the participants, while the second part consists of a set of questions concerned with the knowledge and experience of the participants and their information about the nature of the disease and the virus and its symptoms. The results obtained from the participants was analyzed by SPSS version 21

III. RESULTS

A total of 100 pharmacists and pharmacist assistants participated in the questionnaire, the majority of whom were female (n = 66), (62%) of the participants were between the ages of 30-39, (79%) were married, most of them hold a bachelor's degree by 69%. (47%) of the participants had service from 5 to 10 years.

TABLE 1. Characteristics of the participants

Parameter	n (%)
Sex	Male 34 (34)
	Female 66 (66)
Age	20-29 years 32 (32)
	30-39 years 62 (62)
	40-49 years 12 (12)
	50-59 years 0 (0)
Marital status	Single 21 (21)
	Married 79 (79)
	Other 0 (0)
Education	Diploma 25(25)
	Bachelor 70 (70)
	Master (5)
How many years have you been working?	<5 years 28 (28)
	5-10 years 47 (47)
	11-15 years 16 (16)
	16-20 years and older 6 (6)
	20 and greater 3 (3)

The responses given by participants to the COVID-19 questionnaire are echoed in Table 2.

TABLE 2. Questions on Pharmacists Awareness of covid-19 and Its Symptoms

Question	Answer	n(%)
Have you been infected with covid-19?	Yes	66 (66)
	No	34 (34)
Are you fully aware of the symptoms associated with the Covid-19?	Yes	91 (91)
	No	2 (2)
	Don't know	7 (7)
Do you wear a Covid-19 mask?	Yes	30 (30)
	No	70 (70)
	Don't know	
If you have been exposed to the Corona virus, do you think that the surrounding work environment is the reason?	Yes	80 (80)
	No	11 (11)
	Don't know	9 (9)
Do you stick to frequent hand washing?	Yes	83 (83)
	No	17 (17)
	Don't know	
Do you have enough and updated information about the Corona virus?	yes	89 (89)
	No	11 (11)
	Don't know	
Do you know how the covid-19 virus is transmitted?	Yes	96 (96)
	No	2 (2)
	Don't know	2 (2)
Do you think that leaving a safe distance between you and your colleague protects against infection with the Corona virus?	yes	79 (79)
	No	11 (11)
	Don't know	10 (10)
Taking the vaccine protects against COVID-19?	Yes	47 (47)
	No	41 (41)
	Don't know	12 (12)
What are the best ways to prevent corona virus?	Use of masks and glasses	24 (24)
	Use of hand sanitizers	6 (6)
	Use of special clothes	0 (0)
	Use of medicines such as zinc, Vitamin C	3 (3)
	all mentioned	75 (75)
Do you think that the number of pharmacists in each pharmacy should be reduced to reduce infection with the Corona virus?	yes	10 (10)
	No	88 (88)
	Don't know	2 (2)

Pharmacists Awareness of Covid-19 And Its Symptoms were obtained from the data gathered and analyzed by the software SPSS version 21, their believe that wearing mask and use of hand sanitizer and using medicines such as zinc and vitamin c are the best way to prevent from getting infected by covid-19 by (18.36% and 35.64% respectively) which is not significant.

Awareness of the symptoms associated with the Covid-19 was 30.94% and 60% respectively ($p=.683$), the surrounding work environment is the reason for exposing to the Corona virus was (27.88% and 54.12% respectively $p=.957$).

While they believe that Taking the vaccine protects against COVID-19 was 16% and 30.94% respectively ($p=.00264$) which is significant. There is a commitment of wearing mask, with a significant difference (24.82% and 48.18% $p=.0001$).

Most of the participants have a good and updated data about corona virus and how the virus transmitted. A (79 %) of them think that leaving a safe distance between colleagues protects against infection with the Corona virus.

IV. DISCUSSION

One of the most important responsibilities of pharmacists is to provide medical information for medicines to medical care providers and patients and everyone who is a specialist from nurses and pharmacists in patient affairs.[5] The number of Covid-19 infections and positive cases is still increasing these days and the presence of new mutations, so all health care providers and those who are specialized in this must have complete, accurate and reliable information to present it to the public in a prestigious and correct manner. All those concerned with the health system and health system specialists have the responsibility to encourage members of society to take the utmost precaution and take reasons to prevent the spread of the epidemic and limit exposure to it.[6]

In this study, most of the participants were aware of the ways of transmission of the Corona virus and most of them were also fully aware of the symptoms associated with COVID-19. Most of those who have been exposed to the new Corona virus believe that the surrounding work environment is the main cause of infection.[7]

The source of participants' information about the new Corona virus was through social media, television and official books issued by the work.

Pharmacists' responses regarding reducing the number of pharmacists in each pharmacy to reduce infection with the virus were that there is no point in reducing the number of patients, and that the treatment should be delivered to patients instead of their attendance at the hospital, where this is better prevented, and that the delivery of information and advice about the treatments that were dispensed to patients by phone messages makes a difference Reducing the risk of contracting the virus.[8]

The vast majority of the research participants believe that adhering to social distancing measures, wearing a mask, and using hand sanitizers is very necessary to prevent infection with the emerging corona virus.

V. CONCLUSION

From this study, we conclude that pharmacists and pharmacist assistants at King Hussein Hospital have sufficient awareness of this global epidemic and its accompanying symptoms. This positive and high level of knowledge affects the rest of the people working and not working in this health sector in a positive way.

REFERENCES

- Zhu, N., et al., A Novel Coronavirus from Patients with Pneumonia in China, 2019. *N Engl J Med*, 2020. 382(8): p. 727-733.
- Organization, w.H., Weekly Surveillance Report. Availableat: <http://www.euro.who.int/en/health-topics/health-emergencies/coronavirus-covid-19/weekly-surveillance-report>. Accessed: April 2,2020.
- Lim, J., et al., Case of the Index Patient Who Caused Tertiary Transmission of COVID-19 Infection in Korea: the Application of Lopinavir/Ritonavir for the Treatment of COVID-19 Infected Pneumonia Monitored by Quantitative RT-PCR. *J Korean Med Sci*, 2020. 35(6): p. e79.
- Huang, C., et al., Clinical features of patients infected with 2019 novel coronavirus in Wuhan, China. *Lancet*, 2020. 395(10223): p. 497-506.

5. Ghaibi, S., H. Ipema, and M. Gabay, ASHP guidelines on the pharmacist's role in providing drug information. *Am J Health Syst Pharm*, 2015. 72(7): p. 573-7.
6. Woods, C., et al., "Out of our control": living through Cyclone Yasi. *Int J Qual Stud Health Well-being*, 2014. 9: p. 19821.
7. Zhong, B.-L., et al., Knowledge, attitudes, and practices towards COVID-19 among Chinese residents during the rapid rise period of the COVID-19 outbreak: a quick online cross-sectional survey. *International Journal of Biological Sciences*, 2020. 16(10): p. 1745-1752.
8. Pustokhina, I.V., D.A. Pustokhin, and K. Shankar, A novel machine learning-based detection and diagnosis model for coronavirus disease (COVID-19) using discrete wavelet transform with rough neural network. *Data Science for COVID-19*. 2021:597-612. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-824536-1.00009-5. Epub 2021 May 21.